

Luminous Flux and solid angle through a ball

Harald Schröer

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We take as receiver a ball with radius R . The distance between the light source Q and the ball's midpoint M is r (see both figures). We search the solid

$$r > R$$

angle Ω . The vacuum is assumed here. a is the radius of the solid angle ball. h

is the height of the hatched spherical segment. We use:

$$\Omega[\text{sr}] = \frac{M}{a^2} = \frac{2\pi ah}{a^2} = 2\pi \frac{h}{a} \quad (1)$$

With Euclid's theorem for the right-angled triangle follows:

$$a^2 = r(a - h) \Leftrightarrow \frac{a^2}{r} = a - h \Leftrightarrow h = a - \frac{a^2}{r}$$

Now it is $a^2 = r^2 - R^2$ (see fig.)

$$\Rightarrow h = \sqrt{r^2 - R^2} - \frac{r^2 - R^2}{r}$$

a and h inserted in equation (1):

$$\Omega[\text{sr}] = 2\pi \frac{\sqrt{r^2 - R^2} - \frac{r^2 - R^2}{r}}{\sqrt{r^2 - R^2}}$$

$$\Omega[\text{sr}] = 2\pi \left(1 - \frac{\sqrt{r^2 - R^2}}{r} \right) \quad (2)$$

$$\Omega[\text{sr}] = 2\pi \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{R^2}{r^2}} \right) \quad r > R$$

With constant luminous intensity I the luminous flux through the ball is:

$$\Phi[\text{lm}] = 2\pi I \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{R^2}{r^2}} \right) \quad r > R$$

For $R \ll r$ follows because of

$$\sqrt{1 - \frac{R^2}{r^2}} \approx 1 - \frac{R^2}{2r^2}$$

This is because of the binomial series in Forster [1] §22 at theorem 7 p.182-185.

We get:

$$\Phi[\text{lm}] \approx \pi I \frac{R^2}{r^2}$$

References

- [1] Otto Forster "Analysis 1" 4.Auflage 1984 Vieweg Verlag Brunswick
- [2] Harald Schröer "Luminous Flux and Illumination" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001